

Traceability and Quality Monitoring throughout the Fish Value Chain

D4.1 Risk & Status Assessment Models v1.0

DELIVERABLE NUMBER	D4.1
DELIVERABLE TITLE	Risk and Status Assessment Models v1.0
RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)

TraceMyFish is part of the ERA-NET Cofund BlueBio with funding provided by national sources [i.e., General Secretariat for Research and Innovation in Greece, Research Council of Norway, Innovation Fund Denmark and Icelandic Centre for Research in Iceland] and co-funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, Grant Agreement number 817992.

PROJECT ACRONYM	TraceMyFish
PROJECT FULL NAME	Traceability and Quality Monitoring throughout the Fish Value Chain
STARTING DATE (DUR.)	01/11/2021 (24 months)
ENDING DATE	31/10/2023
COORDINATOR	Panagiotis Zervas
COORDINATOR EMAIL	panagiotis@scio.systems
WORKPACKAGE N. TITLE	WP4 AI models for tracking and tracing
WORKPACKAGE LEADER	SCiO
RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)
RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR EMAIL	antonis@scio.systems
DATE OF DELIVERY (CONTRACTUAL)	31/08/2022
DATE OF DELIVERY (SUBMITTED)	15/11/2022
VERSION STATUS	1.0
NATURE	DEMONSTRATOR
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	PUBLIC
AUTHORS (PARTNER)	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO), Christos Charisis (SCiO)
CONTRIBUTORS	-
REVIEWER	Panagiotis Zervas (SCiO)

VERSION	MODIFICATION(S)	DATE	AUTHOR(S)
vo.1	ToC	17.08.2022	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)
vo.2	Historical Data Analysis section	01.09.2022	Christos Charisis (SCiO)
vo.6	Algorithmic Approaches section	15.09.2022	Christos Charisis (SCiO)
vo.8	Full draft	15.10.2022	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)
vo.9	Internal review	01.11.2022	Panagiotis Zervas (SCiO)
v1.0	Document finalised and submitted	15.11.2022	Panagiotis Zervas (SCiO)

PARTICIPANTS		CONTACT PERSON
<p>SCiO P.C. (SCiO, Greece) Coordinator</p>		<p>Panagiotis Zervas E-mail: panagiotis@scio.systems</p>
<p>Department of Food Science and Human Nutrition, Agricultural University of Athens (AUA, Greece)</p>		<p>George-John Nychas E-mail: gjn@aua.gr</p>
<p>Department of Biotechnology and Food, Norwegian University of Science and Technology Science (NTNU, Norway)</p>		<p>Jørgen Lerfall E-mail: jorgen.lerfall@ntnu.no</p>
<p>Videometer A/S (VIDEOM, Denmark)</p>		<p>Nette Schultz E-mail: NS@videometer.com</p>
<p>Faculty of Food Science and Nutrition, University of Iceland (UoI, Iceland)</p>		<p>Maria Guðjónsdóttir E-mail: mariagu@hi.is</p>
<p>Matis (MATIS, Iceland)</p>		<p>Hildur Inga Sveinsdóttir E-mail: hilduringa@matis.is</p>

ACRONYMS LIST

ML	Machine Learning
IoT	Internet-of-Things
CNN	Convolutional Neural Networks
CLNN	Cascade Learning Networks

TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF FIGURES.....	6
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	7
1 INTRODUCTION.....	8
2 EXPLORATORY ANALYSIS OF HISTORICAL DATA.....	9
3 CANDIDATE ALGORITHMIC APPROACHES.....	10
4 FUTURE TARGETS AND ACTION PLAN.....	11

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Snippet of Literature Analysis Document.....	9
--	---

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present report summarises the exploratory analysis of different algorithmic solutions for the predictive analysis of fish product status in the fish value chains targeted by TraceMyFish and the relevant iFMS developed by the project.

The report summarises the findings from the analysis of historical data and describes the different families of algorithms that have been implemented and deployed in the TraceMyFish data platform, to be trained and used in the context of the TraceMyFish pilots.

1 INTRODUCTION

TraceMyFish aims to advance supply system in three geographically distributed blue bioeconomy value chains, by designing and implementing an iFish Management System (iFMS) that will allow the tracking and tracing of safety and quality-critical information across the links of the targeted value chains. Moreover, the TraceMyFish iFMS will establish a secure, trust-enabled data infrastructure, which will collect, pre-process and analyse data coming from innovative, portable sensing devices of different nature and modality (spectral imaging, variegating IoT sensors) and informing specialized AI models and architecture that will enable timely risk prediction to different value chain actors. The examined fish products will carry smart barcodes that, in communication with the iFMS, will carry safety information related to each product and will allow stakeholders and consumers to easily and reliably access this information at any time.

Towards this objective, Work Package 4, Risk and Status Assessment Models, aims to design, train and deploy the machine learning components that will perform the predictive analysis to assess the status and quality of a fish product as it goes through the value chains targeted by TraceMyFish. It builds on the scientific analyses of WP2 and the experimental designs and protocols to be employed in WP6, to identify important features, and define targeted variables and collaborates closely with WP3 to clarify the association of experimentally observed features with measurements taken as the value chain progresses. Finally, it follows the architectural choices of WP5 to appropriately package and integrate the software components that operationalise the machine learning solutions.

The present documents summarises the actions taken thus far to design and deploy the relevant models. The exploratory analysis of historical data is presented in section 2. A brief summary of good candidate algorithms that have been examined in presented in section 3. Finally, future activities and targets are presented in section 4.

2 EXPLORATORY ANALYSIS OF HISTORICAL DATA

The first step towards the specification of the predictive models to be incorporated in TraceMyFish was a comprehensive analysis of the currently applied approaches and the respective input data as acquired by laboratory experiments. To achieve this, 43 scientific publications were provided by WP2, spanning a period from 2009 to 2022. The publications were analysed in terms of data acquisition techniques, analytical approaches that were used, and their targeted ML problem.

A	B	C	D	E	F	G
Title	File name	Year	Data Acquisition Technique	Algorithm(s) used	Comments	ML category
Estimation of the Microbiological Quality of Meat Using Rapid and Non-Invasive Spectroscopic Sensors	249 (2020) Fengou et al IEEE	2020	Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, Multispectral imaging (MSI)	Support Vector Regression (SVR)	Assessing minced pork meat microbiological quality	Regression
Machine learning workflow for raw food spectroscopic classification in a future industry	251 (2020) Tsakanikas et al Scientific Report	2020	Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy	Support Vector Machine (SVM) on Partial Least Squares Regression feature extraction	Multi-class classification of 7 different types of raw food (beef, pork, chicken, farmed whole ungutted gilthead sea bream, ready-to-eat rocket, baby-spinach and pinapple)	Classification
Microbiological assessment of aerobically stored horse fillets through predictive microbiology and metabolomic approach	253 (2021) Pavlidis et al Meat Sc (horse)	2021	HS-SPME/GC-MS, HPLC-PDA-R	Support Vector Regression (SVR)	Investigate the microbial association of horse fillets during aerobic storage at isothermal conditions	Regression
Rapid detection of minced pork and chicken adulteration in fresh, stored and cooked ground meat	257 Di (2021) Fengou et al Food Control poultry vs pork	2021	Multispectral Imaging (MSI)	Support Vector Machines (SVM)	Detection of minced pork with chicken (and vice versa) adulteration in raw fresh, raw stored and cooked minced meat (classes are the percentage of adulteration)	Classification
Microbial Quality Assessment of Chicken Liver Inoculated or Not With Salmonella Using FTIR Spectroscopy and Machine Learning	259(2021) Dourou et al Frontiers ML	2021	Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy	Support Vector Regression (SVR)	Assess chicken liver microbiological quality	Regression
Intelligent Research Tools for Rapid Evaluation of Fish Quality: FTIR Spectroscopy and Multispectral Imaging Versus Microbiological Analysis	261 (2021) Govari et al foods-10-00264	2021	Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, Multispectral Imaging (MSI)	Partial Least Squares Regression (PLS-R)	Assess the microbiological quality of farmed sea bass (fish) fillets stored under aerobic conditions and modified atmosphere packaging	Regression
Spoilage assessment of chicken breast fillets by means of fourier transform infrared spectroscopy and multispectral image analysis	262 (2021) Spyrelli et al CRFS	2021	Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, Multispectral Imaging (MSI)	Partial Least Squares Regression (PLS-R)	Assessment of spoilage on the surface of chicken breast fillets.	Regression
Detection of Meat Adulteration Using Spectroscopy-Based Sensors	266 Di (2021) Fengou et al foods-10-00861	2021	Fluorescence (FLUO), Visible (VIS) spectroscopic, Hyper/Multispectral imaging	Support Vector Machines (SVM)	Detecting fraudulent minced meat substitution, of beef with bovine offal and pork with chicken (and vice versa) both in fresh and frozen-thawed samples	Classification
Data Science in the Food Industry	268 (2021) Nychas et al An Rev Biom Sci	2021	high-performance liquid chromatography, gas chromatography, high-performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry, gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), nuclear magnetic resonance, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), Raman spectrometry, sensors in ultraviolet (UV), near-infrared (NIR), mid-infrared, and visual (VIS) ranges, multi and hyperspectral imaging sensors	Support Vector Machines (SVM), Genetic Algorithms (GA), Partial Least-Squares Discriminant Analysis (PLS-DA), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)	Interesting Review on the subject, with a detailed table with applications of ML on food adulteration etc.	-
Microbiological Quality Assessment of Chicken Thigh Fillets Using Spectroscopic Sensors and Multivariate Data Analysis	270 (2021) Spyrelli et al foods	2021	Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, Multispectral Imaging (MSI)	Partial least squares regression (PLS-R), Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), Quadratic Discriminant Analysis (QDA), Support Vector Machines (SVMs), Quadratic Support Vector Machines (QSVMs)	Prediction of the microbiological quality of poultry meat	Regression + Classification
Spectroscopy and imaging technologies coupled with machine learning for the assessment of the microbiological spoilage associated to ready-to-eat leafy vegetables	271 (2022) Manthou et al leafy products	2022	Fourier transform infrared (FTIR), Near-infrared (NIR), Visible (VIS),	Partial Least Squares Regression (PLSR), Support Vector Regression (SVR)	Evaluating the microbiological spoilage of ready-to eat leafy vegetables (baby spinach and rocket)	Regression

Figure 1: Snippet of Literature Analysis Document

Additionally, data from 50 laboratory experiments on salmon, seabass, and seabream aiming to associate microbial count with hyperspectral measurements were delivered to the model implementation team, in order to provide a first set of ground truth / training data to the models. These were used for testing different AI approaches, as reported in the next section. It has to be noted that the purpose of this training was to determine the best approaches for the dimensionality and volume of the data to be used, as the actual models to be operationalised will rely solely on measurements able to be obtained in the value chains progression. Thus, the full modelling solution will also entail models for the association of these complex laboratory measurements with the restricted in-motion measurements taken over the value chain steps.

3 CANDIDATE ALGORITHMIC APPROACHES

In summary, the AI solution fit for TraceMyFish should cover both broad categories of AI problems: a *regression* problem, aiming to estimate the values of the target parameters given different experimental conditions (inputs); and a *classification* problem (under investigation) where the candidate classes correspond to the acceptability or non-acceptability status of a product.

In this respect, we examine and operationalise different algorithmic solutions that adhere to the two problems and the nature and volume of data to be available in the context of the project. Indicative technologies to be tested are the following.

1. **Partial Least Squares regression (PLS):** the method reduces the variables used to predict, to a smaller set of predictors. These predictors are then used to perform a (linear) regression. It is widely used in domains relevant to TraceMyFish, such as bioinformatics and sensometrics.
2. **Least Mean Squares regression (LMS):** the Least Squares family of algorithms aim to approximate given values by incrementally finding an optimal fitting function between them and the input variables. Optimality is determined by minimising an error function over the residuals (i.e., differences between given and observed values). LMS is one of the most potent approaches for this minimisation problem and can use different variations of gradient descent approaches for the tested functions.
3. **Support Vector Regression (SVR):** In accordance with the general principles of Support Vector Machines, the basic idea behind SVR is to find the best fit line for a dataset. In SVR, the best fit line is the hyperplane that has the maximum number of points. Unlike other regression models that try to minimize the error between the real and predicted value, the SVR tries to fit the best line within a threshold value. It is thus best suitable for relatively low-volume datasets, as it is not computationally scalable, but has good performance on limited volume sets.
4. **Random Forests:** Random forests is a Supervised Machine Learning Algorithm, and specifically an ensemble learning method, that is used widely in both classification and regression problems. It builds decision trees on different samples and takes their majority vote for classification and average in case of regression. While it generally performs better in classification problems, the approach can produce good result to regression problems where there are not explicitly stated correlation between the input variables. Thus, this is a stronger candidate for the classification variance of the TraceMyFish prediction problem.

All the above techniques can be incorporated in or combined with different architectures of Neural Networks and different training paradigms, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Cascade Learning Networks (CLNN). We will test different connectivity and training techniques in the context of experimenting with the different approaches.

In the cases of techniques that require a relatively larger amount of data for their proper training, we will use synthetic datasets produced via stochastic generators and based on the realistic data samples reported by the laboratory experiments. However, this requires the execution of the full range of the foreseen experiments, to ensure that they reflect with better precision the distribution and statistical correlation of the tracked product features.

At this stage, implementations of all aforementioned techniques have been produced and deployed in the TraceMyFish data platform, with a non-calibrated hyperparameter specification. These are to be further tested and fine-tuned as data from experimental sessions and pilots are ingested into the system.

4 FUTURE TARGETS AND ACTION PLAN

As data streams and measurement capacity is concretised in the context of the TraceMyFish pilots, the immediate action path for Work Package 4 is the further testing and calibration of the implemented modules with realistic data derived from laboratory experiments in combination with the execution of value chain simulations in the context of WP6. These are the main inputs required for the evolution of the models and their stabilisation. Additionally, we will investigate in collaboration with WP2 the possibility of handling classification problems over the targeted value chains, and accordingly adapt the models to perform the classification tasks. All results will be available via the TraceMyFish data platform, integrated in accordance with the reported architecture and operationalised in the context of the second round of TraceMyFish pilots.